

Editorial

Embracing Open Science: Marie Curie Alumni Leading the Way in Research Accessibility and Impact

Dear MCAA colleagues/members,

Beneficiaries of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) during Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020. During these two research funding programmes, the EU and the MSCA have been strongly promoting Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation. Much of the focus was initially on Open Access publication but this then led to an increased focus on how to make research accessible to all audiences in ways that can lead to increased real-world impact.

This special newsletter issue explores how MSCA Alumni engage with Open Science. In this introductory article, we will cover key elements of open science, practical benefits of adopting open science practices and challenges, as well as policy developments and support, illustrated by examples from authors' stories.

Understanding Open Science in its many forms

Open Science represents a paradigm shift in how research is conducted, disseminated, and utilized. It emphasizes transparency, collaboration, and accessibility, allowing broader participation and fostering innovation.

In 2021 UNESCO issued a first international recommendation after conducting a global consultation

“Central to the Recommendation is a set of pillars holding up a global open science system: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems, in combination with science communication.” (from Recommendation on Open Science. UNESCO General Conference, November 2021. Paris: UNESCO Publishing.)

Figure 1 shows these elements, commonly associated with science and research.

Open Access: ensure research outputs are freely available to everyone without subscription barriers.

Open Data: share research data openly, free to access, re-use and modify and in formats that adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, enabling others to validate and build upon findings.

Open Methodology: make research workflows, protocols, lab notebooks, and software openly available to enhance reproducibility.

Figure 1. From Recommendation on Open Science. UNESCO General Conference, November 2021. Paris: UNESCO Publishing.

Open Source software: allows free access to distribution of software and access to the source code

Open Educational Resources: develop and share learning materials and tools to support knowledge dissemination.

Open collaboration and citizen science encourage the active involvement of the public in the research process in the form of citizen science projects, whether through data collection, analysis, or dissemination.

Open Infrastructure: development of tools, platforms, and networks that support Open Science practices (open repository like arXiv for preprints, data sharing platforms like OSF and FigShare)

Open Hardware: design and sharing of physical objects, tools, or devices (e.g., Lab equipment, 3D printing models)... further making available for modification and reuse.

Open Evaluation: transparent assessment of research outputs, including grants, proposals, or projects.

Open Peer Review: opening up the peer review of journal articles.

Practical benefits of Open Science

Open Science allows publicly-funded research to maximise its impact and transfer into real-world impact by making the outputs of research open for use and study. Openness reduces barriers to knowledge transfer. Maria Lorena Falco's contribution radiates enthusiasm about articles available through Open Access. Another contributor, Natalia Mishyna proves how publishing Open Access boosted the visibility of her research, increased citations and connected her expertise with policymakers.

Openness also means that duplication of research can be avoided, so that research funding can be better used for more novel topics. Open Science, as highlighted during the [COVID-19 pandemic](#), leads to more rapid scientific progress. This in turn leads to better use of research funding and quicker commercialisation of research.

Openness leads to increased reproducibility of research results. Open access to research data, protocols, code and other details of experimental design, facilitates verification of research results, greater transparency and increased public trust in science. Open science practices prove that research is not purely academic endeavour but a force for public good.

Newsletter contribution by Linda Belkessa highlights how Open Data fuels the future

of urban mobility, making cities greener and more connected how real-time data sharing for urban mobility improvements. In another article, Kannan Govindaraj gives an account of how impactful communication of science to the general public can be, through his story of writing in the local language newspaper in India.

MCAA is an association whose members have benefitted from EU research funding in the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. Nevertheless, MCAA members come from almost all countries globally and many choose to work outside the EU after the end of their fellowship. Open Science aims to make the fruits of research accessible to an audience worldwide regardless of the differences of funding between research ecosystems in the Global North and Global South.

An excellent example of how Open Science can produce practical real-world impact is the work of Eugenio Otal, an Assistant Professor at Shinshu University in Japan, to help secure the safety of drinking water in rural Africa by making the design of his low-cost Arduino-based fluoride sensor available as an Open Hardware design. Openness accelerates the uptake of research results globally and leads to real-world societal, economic, health and environmental impacts.

Furthermore, Danielle Marie Agnello shares how she was encouraged to create a global collaboration platform connecting researchers across 19 countries. "What began as an open-access [MSCA] requirement quickly turned into an opportunity to create something valuable", she emphasizes.

What could stay in the way of adopting Open Science by researchers?

Despite its advantages, Open Science faces several obstacles that researchers must navigate, such as technological and logistical barriers, cultural resistance, funding

constraints, ethical and legal concerns, and recognition and career impact.

Less commonly discussed, adoption of Open Science practices can impact researchers' mental health, adding pressures and vulnerabilities. These challenges are sometimes specific to Early Career Stage (ECR) and established researchers.

...for ECRs:

- **Career progression and metrics:** traditional academic metrics often overlook contributions like data sharing or preprints, leading to anxiety about career advancement.
- **Resource constraints:** limited funding for Open Access publishing fees (APC), data duration costs and data management tools can be challenging for most researchers.
- **Fear of criticism and credibility concerns:** public sharing of data and preprints invites scrutiny, fear of being scooped or not being taken seriously by peers, leading to anxiety and can amplify perfectionist tendencies, causing stress.
- **Limited support:** advisors or institutions may not prioritize Open Science, and such lack of support and guidance may lead ECRs to manifest feelings of isolation and disconnection.

... for established researchers:

- **Stress from cultural resistance:** long-standing practices and scepticism can hinder the willingness to adopt Open Science and slow its progress, and adapting to Open Science after years of traditional methods can be frustrating.
- **Increased performance pressure:** balancing traditional metrics and Open Science contributions can be overwhelming, and balancing new practices with existing responsibilities can lead to burnout.
- **Public accountancy and risk of reputation:** sharing data openly invites scrutiny, raising

Image by Midjourney, prompt by Fabrizio Martina

concerns about public criticism, and thus fear of criticism of mistakes may deter participation.

- **Infrastructural barriers:** gaps in resources and support for Open Science workflow.
- **Complex collaborations and conflict with colleagues:** coordinating openness within multidisciplinary teams can be challenging, often diverging views on Open Science within teams can lead to tension.

..shared challenges:

- **Ethical and legal concerns:** issues around data privacy, intellectual property, and misinterpretation of openly shared data create uncertainties and frustration.
- **Misaligned incentives and career impact:** reward systems & evaluation metrics often favor traditional publishing over transparency and contributions to Open Science, creating tensions for researchers
- **Imposter syndrome due to lack of training:** (i) learning new tools and platforms requires time and training (ii) maintaining data repositories and ensuring FAIR compliance can be resource-intensive. Traditional education systems don't provide exposure to tools and workflows essential for Open Science, and lack of exposure to them can amplify self-doubt.
- **Perceived trade-offs:** balancing openness with competitive pressures in academia requires additional time disruption work-life balance and can lead to exhaustion/burnout.

Navigating institutional and systemic barriers

Publishing practices

The uptake of Open Science is largely challenged by the inertia of research culture to change through the interests of stakeholders to preserve the previous system. Journal publishing has been an extremely lucrative system and the leading publishing houses and journals have been forced to transition to an alternative business model by moving from journal subscriptions to a model based on article processing charges. This is complicated by different subsidies for libraries and researchers in different countries in Europe and globally. The adoption of Open Access publishing is still not completed but has already led to a fundamental change to the academic publishing business and increased access to scientific knowledge.

Implementation challenges and initiatives

Speaking of the Open Data pillar, Marianna Chimienti shares reflection on the evolution of open science practices in the ecology field and importance of proper infrastructures. On other hand, Irène Arrata shares insights from her challenging experience as a project manager implementing FAIR data principles and a Data Management Plan in a chemistry consortium.

Daniela Saderi describes the work of PRReview to democratize scholarly communication, to make peer review more transparent and equitable, an Open Peer Review pillar. Paola Masuzzo and Ivo Grigorov, on other hand, discuss the controversies of publishing research proposal open (yes, Open Proposals), with tips on strategic implementation of this practice.

Many researchers report that a very practical barrier to the uptake of Open Science is the lack of support through funding and training to prepare them to embrace Open Science. As MSCA fellow Christina Makoundou asserts in her story - "Open Science should be the standard, not a privilege reserved for those with specific funding or resources". Nataša Jakominić Marot describes how the participation of the University of Rijeka in the OPUS project has led to the provision of training and educational resources that support academics to practice Open Science. Shanmugapriya Periyannan shares an inspiring story of learning more about diverse Open Science pillars in a global virtual training that was funded within a framework of [NASA TOPS programme](#).

Research assessment reform

A major challenge to the uptake of Open Science practices is that research assessment by research funders and academic hiring committees have derived insight into researcher performance through metrics related to peer-reviewed publications, primarily journal impact factor and h-index. These metrics have granted legitimacy to funding and hiring decisions and ostensibly allowed institutions to take decisions that avoided conflicts of interest. Nevertheless, these metrics have many limitations. Citation metrics disadvantage early-career researchers, who have developed genuinely novel research, but have not had time to acquire a high number of citations. Metrics lead some researchers to try to game the system by prioritising quality over quantity. For instance, it encourages salami slicing of research into the "[least-publishable unit](#)". Using journal impact factor to assess researchers uses a measure of prestige as assessment rather than the actual content of their own research.

The emergence of Open Science in Europe has led to a movement to reform research assessment, so that best practices can be

developed that facilitate responsible research assessment that incentivises the uptake of Open Science practices. Without reform of research assessment, many early career researchers might be reluctant to prioritise open science practices that do not contribute to their academic career development. The MCAA has represented the interests of its members through being an active advocate for reform of research assessment and is involved in many initiatives including CoARA, PEP-CV and the OPUS project.

From policy to practice and back

Research funders have incentivized the uptake of Open Science by making Open Access and Research Data Management requirements for acquiring and managing research funding. In this Newsletter, Alina Irimia from the largest research funder in Romania UEFISCDI, describes how they are shaping the uptake of Open Science at a national level.

Researcher-led initiatives have already contributed to the uptake of Open Science practices. The MCAA, Eurodoc and the Young Academy of Europe joined together in 2019 to [respond to the publication of the Open Access initiative Plan S](#).

Former researchers, now Policy experts James Morris (Science Europe) and Annelies Van de Ven (MSCA) independently note the broadening of Open Science beyond the traditional Open Access and Open Data to emerging elements like open research methods or public engagement and emphasize that open science requirements should be beneficial to researchers rather than burdening, while ensuring effective monitoring by administrators.

Moving together

This special issue brings together diverse voices from researchers practising open science, educators, research administrators

and policymakers. It highlights the wide spectrum of Open Science practices that MCAA members have built into their research. It shows how embracing Open Science can increase reproducibility, democratise access to research results, accelerate scientific progress, facilitate real-world impact, increase public trust in science and enhance research collaboration globally.

To continue moving together, Theodota Lagiuri and the MCAA Policy Working Group welcome your contributions to the Thematic Group on Open Science Policy, while MCAA regional chapters and Working Groups offer opportunities to share perspectives and solutions from your specific contexts.

Let us embrace this challenge and opportunity to create a lasting impact. By working together and supporting one another in our Open Science movement, we can achieve a future where Open Science becomes the standard way of doing science benefiting researchers, the research ecosystem and society at large.

And for this, we would like to thank all authors for their contribution to this initiative and the entire MCAA Newsletter team for their assistance.

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